

IMPROVING PROGNOSTIC RESULTS OF BREAST CANCER (BASED ON IHC RESULTS)

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Objective: This study aims to evaluate the effect of neoadjuvant chemotherapy (NACT) on changes in immunohistochemical (IHC) receptor status and its association with overall and disease-free survival in patients with locally advanced breast cancer (BC).

Materials and methods: The study included 115 patients with locally advanced breast cancer who received treatment at the Tashkent city branch of the Republican Scientific and Practical Medical Center. The patients were divided into two groups: the main group (66 patients with changes in IHC status after NACT) and the control group (49 patients without changes in IHC status after NACT). IHC status was analyzed before and after NACT, and statistical analysis was carried out using the StatTech v program. 4.0.4.

Results: In the study group, the average overall survival was 3 years compared to 2.5 years in the control group. Relapse-free survival in the study group was also higher, with a median of 2 years, versus 1.5 years in the control group.

Conclusions: These studies indicate a potentially positive effect of NACT on improving treatment outcomes in patients with locally advanced breast cancer, however, changes in IHC status require additional analysis in the context of its prognostic value. Further research is needed to confirm the results obtained and to introduce the accumulated data into clinical practice, taking into account the role of the patients' age, their general health and concomitant diseases.